

THE ROLE OF METONYMY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROVERBS IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *This article explores the proverbs of the Russian language and the role of literary devices in the development of proverbs. The author of this article wants to give information about metonymy and show how important metonymy is in the development of Russian proverbs.*

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Stylistic means include metaphors, metonymy, personifications, comparisons, gradations that form the content of proverbs and most vividly, figuratively, accurately convey the generalized meaning of proverbs. But today I want to talk about metonymy, because it is one of the main and more important tropes.

Metonymy is the transfer of properties from one object to another on the basis of adjacency. What is adjacency? Adjacent - having a common border with something or less often located next to something.

1. I drank three glasses. Here it is clear that I did not drink glasses, but drank what was in these glasses. For example: water or juice, Why is drinking three glasses a metonymy? Because water and glass are adjacent to each other.

2. The whole audience applauded me. Here it is clear that the hall cannot applaud, because the hall is a room, the people who were in this hall applauded me. This hall and the people were adjacent, and that's how metonymy came about.

How does metonymy arise? It arises as a result of an ellipsis or contraction. For example, I ate two bowls of soup.

Then there was a contraction, that is, something left this proposal. The sentence tightened up and it turned out "I ate two plates" and the result was a metonymy. We, when we perceive this metonymy, we understand perfectly well that we are not talking about plates, but about what was in the plates.

1. Have more brains in one's little finger than one has in the whole body.

2. Sees people behind the forest, but he doesn't see the floor with his nose. - У людей за лесом видит, а у себя – под носом не видит.

3. With someone else's hands you row the boat, but you don't take it cold with your own - Чужими руками жар гребёшь, а своими и холодно не берёшь.

In these examples, quantitative metonymy, part of the whole denotes the whole and is subject to personification. The discrepancy between the internal plan in these proverbs: a person does not notice his hefty shortcomings, a person tries to appropriate someone else's work, an intelligent person is smart in everything, and the external plan leads to the creation of a comic situation.

A well-fed belly is deaf to learning – Сытое брюхо к ученью тупо.

It means that in order to briskly go uphill, powerful motivation is required, and hunger well motivates a person to an outstanding climb up the social ladder. For the "millionaire from the slums", hunger is useful only at the beginning of the journey, later it

is superfluous and undesirable, only unpleasant memories of hungry youth can be preserved, they will save them from wastage and careless investments of capital.

Metonymy is a kind of trope when one word is replaced by another, with which there is an association or some kind of connection. This name is a turn of speech, phrases with a figurative meaning. With metonymy, two words are replaced that are related and close in meaning. Metonymy itself arises through the contraction of a phrase, that is, an ellipsis. The role of metonymy is that it contributes to the reduction and contraction of speech. Unlike metaphor, metonymy is based on juxtaposition, concepts, actions, contiguity with objects that are nothing like each other. As an example of metonymy, we can cite the following Russian proverbs with translations and meanings. In the proverbs shown below, body parts and organs are named instead of the function they perform.

1. Язык мой - враг мой, наперёд ума лепечет.- My tongue is my enemy, my mind babbles in advance.

The proverb says that the tongue is sometimes the main enemy of man. Sometimes we say without thinking what we should not have said, and this leads us to bad consequences when dealing with people.

2. Язык без костей: скажет и обратно спрячется.- Tongue without bones: he will say and hide back.

This proverb also talks about a language that has no boundaries when talking or about people who like to talk and chat about all sorts of nonsense. After all, people should follow their tongue and spoken words.

3. Язык голову кормит, он же и до беды доводит.- The tongue feeds the head, it also leads to trouble.

The proverb says that you can earn money with the language, teach it, or you can receive insults and complaints for bad words, saying unnecessary words or gossip.

4. С глаз долой – из сердца вон.- Out of sight, out of mind.

The meaning of this proverb is that everything is forgotten, but sometimes it passes quite quickly. We should part with a person, and we are already losing interest in him.

5. Глаза – зеркало души.- Eyes are the mirror of the soul.

A proverb is about a person's eyes, which play an essential role in the art of recognizing people, they represent the most informative component of appearance in the eyes, reflecting the character traits of past experience and even the intellectual capabilities of a person. So, they are the mirror of the soul.

6. Рука руку моет.- Hand washes hand.

This proverb is about the relationship of people in any business, when they cover up the reprehensible actions of each other. It is also associated with the dishonesty of participants in exchange trading and expressions indicating possible fraud.

There are also proverbs with metonymy, the allegorism of which is based on the contiguity of phenomena, most often on the replacement of the whole by a part, often metonymic transfer is carried out using nouns denoting parts of the body, for example:

1. В чужих руках ломать велик.-In the hands of others, the chunk is great.

Means that you need to be able to appreciate what you have, and try to achieve more only with your own work, and not envy other people's successes.

2. Дурная голова ногам покоя не даёт.- A bad head does not give rest to the legs.

It is said about those who, without thinking through their actions, fuss in vain.

3. За его языком не поспеешь и босиком.- You can't keep up with his tongue even barefoot.

It is said jokingly to someone (or about someone) who is excessively talkative and talkative.

4. На всякий роток не накинешь платок.- You can't throw a scarf over every mouth.
The meaning of the saying lies on the surface and is probably understandable to many - it means not paying attention to what people say about you. When action, deeds, words come from the being, what others think about it is not important.

5. Повинную голову и меч не сечёт.- A guilty head a sword does not flog.
Means that a person who himself confessed, admitted his misconduct, is not severely punished and the punishment is mitigated.

Metonymy of place is also found in proverbs, for example:

1. Дом не велик, а лежать не велит.- The house is not large, but it does not order to lie down.

The meaning of this proverb can be understood from the following definitions of the words: order, yes, house, lie down, not, small, house. It is also worth looking at synonymous proverbs on the topic "Surveillance of the Master" - the meaning can be explained in them.

2. Дом дому не указ.- The house is not a decree to the house.

House to house (master to master) is not a decree (not a pointer).

Metonymic transfer to the context of the proverb can be perceived as a metaphor.
For example: Whatever the city, then the habit, whatever the village, then the custom.

From the foregoing, we can conclude that metonymy plays a very important role in proverbs. It is used to increase the imagery and clarity of the situations described. It allows you to influence the mind with greater force for more effective achievement of didactic goals. The study of metonymy in Russian proverbs allows you to get closer to the culture and way of thinking. This will also help to determine the colossal significance of metonymy in them.

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